

Understanding How Researchers Find Research Software for Research Practice

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Research software is gaining recognition as a critical research input and output. To better understand how researchers find software to use or build upon, we surveyed them to find out their software discovery mechanisms and their searching behaviours. Our survey leveraged existing studies, which we tailored for Australia.

The survey revealed the following:

- Our respondents rated research software as “essential” to research.
- The main reasons respondents searched for software to reuse were to save effort and time.
- Respondents used various approaches to find software:
 - The most popular approach was to use generalist search engines such as Google.
 - More traditional academic approaches, such as asking peers for recommendations, were also very popular.

These top searching preferences were consistent across different domains and regardless of whether the respondent was a coder or not.

- Hindrances that respondents encountered when searching for software varied depending on their level of familiarity with coding:
 - For non-coders, the challenges were often that they did not know how to search and how to evaluate the search results.
 - For coders, the challenge was most often that their requirements were “unique”.
- Hindrances also differed for respondents in different domains. A higher percentage of humanities, arts and social sciences (HASS) and Indigenous studies researchers encountered skill-related searching challenges than environmental researchers, who were more often challenged by an inability to access software referenced in publications.
- When searching for code, the most important software characteristics for respondents were the description of functionality, the price and the documentation. The survey results also reveal how useful respondents find software registries.

There are opportunities for software infrastructure providers to address some of the challenges researchers encounter. Possible actions include enhancing institutional repositories and other topical registries, in addition to providing skill development opportunities for researchers to do research software searches more efficiently. These actions could inform priority areas for the development of relevant national infrastructure and make it easier for researchers to discover existing software.

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1. BACKGROUND

There is growing acknowledgment that research software is a critical research enabler¹. Research software can include scripts, code, notebooks, computational workflows, libraries, modules, frameworks, utilities and applications. In line with this view, the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)² has established a National Agenda for Research Software³ in Australia to recognise research software as a first-class research output fundamental to research. Making research software and code visible is an action of the agenda, to ensure researchers can find and use the software they need to improve their research efficiency and reduce duplication of efforts.

Software is critical to modern research, for generating and analysing digital data^{4,5}. Software is also increasingly an output of research, with approximately a third of research resulting in new code⁶. To be useful to research practice, research software must first be discoverable. Effective discoverability of software generated for or by research benefits a large cohort of stakeholders over and above researcher end users, including research funding bodies, research institutions and infrastructure providers.

- **Researchers:** Better software visibility benefits research by decreasing duplication of development effort through the reuse of existing solutions, and increases productivity by decreasing the time taken to work with data. Increased findability of software developed through research can lead to monetary rewards (commercial software), academic reputation and software subfield advances (publishing papers on software alongside domain research)⁷. With impact and engagement being increasingly valued, demonstrating the impact⁸ of research software in social, technological, environmental and economic spheres and its broader adoption across disciplines is important. The challenge here is that the creation of tools such as software is not sufficiently rewarded as a research contribution or output⁹.
- **Research institutions:** Research software discoverability enables greater research reproducibility; when the data and code that were used to generate published results are shared, researchers and institutions have evidence to support their research claims.
- **Research funding bodies:** Because research generates software, funding bodies get more return on investment when the research software is visible and used more broadly across research communities. Software discoverability also gives funders visibility of the volume of software generated through funded research. Increased visibility of the impact of research software, including the breadth of researchers benefiting from the software, also enables more informed decision-making on distributing funding.
- **Infrastructure providers:** Infrastructure providers benefit from their research software offerings being readily found and used by researchers. They also benefit from easy discovery of new software for potential inclusion in service catalogues.

While the benefits of easily discoverable research software are clear for several stakeholders, most research software is not easily findable, having been produced for a specific research project purpose with no extended life beyond the project in mind. Understanding how researchers look for and find software is a critical step to provide insight into better ways to enable research software discoverability and (re)use. Previous studies have investigated this issue¹⁰ and more recently Michael Hucka and Matthew Graham researched this in 2018¹¹. In our study, we leveraged these investigations to gain further insight into the Australian research software findability landscape.

2. SURVEY DESIGN AND DISTRIBUTION

2.1 Survey Design

In commissioning this report, the ARDC was keen to be able to compare and contrast the results with those by Hucka and Graham in 2018, to determine any similarities and differences to the Australian landscape. There were benefits and limitations to this approach.

- **Benefits:** Reusing an existing survey enables monitoring of research software approaches across time, domains and geography.
- **Limitations:** In a sector where 4–5 years may see a broad shift in technology and maturity, the survey questions from 2018 may no longer be appropriate. They also limit our ability to interrogate specificities of the Australian perspective.

As a result of the limitations raised above, we made minor changes to some of the Hucka and Graham questions. We also changed the survey in line with feedback received on a review of the draft survey. Volunteer reviewers provided feedback on topics such as clarity, time taken to complete, and appropriateness for research circumstances. The reviewers provided a range of perspectives based on their expertise, which included science communication, research infrastructure experience, workforce development skills, research software engineering, data governance, machine learning and prior research experience. Future survey drafts would benefit from design feedback loops from a sampling of the target audience, in this case active researchers.

The number of questions seen by respondents was conditional on their answers to prior questions; for example, respondents who indicated they did not code were not presented with 4 questions relating to coding practice. Choice randomisation was also carried out on 4 of the questions with lengthier lists of options to eliminate bias generated by option presentation (Questions 1, 2, 3 and 6 see DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353418>). The most pertinent questions on software findability were asked upfront in the survey to minimise the impact of dropout attrition on the study results, thereby leaving demographic questions to the end of the survey. The final survey (see DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353418>) consisted of 22 questions (9 optional), the last 4 optional questions were administrative (first name, last name, email, select to be contacted), which we have removed from the dataset (see DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353422>).

2. SURVEY DESIGN AND DISTRIBUTION

2.2 Survey Distribution

The desired audience for our survey included researchers, and researchers who code; differing somewhat from the target audience of the Hucka and Graham study whose overall motivation was to understand how scientists and engineers find software. Their 2018 study was oriented to the biological and astronomical sciences and the computational subcommunities within these domains, targeted through forums and mailing lists. For our study, we wanted to elicit responses from all research disciplines, given that researchers across many domains spend a portion of their time developing code and software for research.

We published the survey via SurveyMonkey and distributed it according to a marketing and communications strategy that targeted the ARDC newsletter¹², targeted emails and ARDC social media announcements (Twitter¹³ and LinkedIn¹⁴). The survey was directly sent to 1,010 people of whom 782 were researchers and 228 were research support staff. The research support staff were requested to socialise the survey with researchers. The survey was also distributed to the Visible Research Software Interest Group¹⁵ via its public discussion forum¹⁶; the Research Software Engineer Association of Australia and New Zealand¹⁷; the ARDC Research Platforms community mailing list; and National Research Infrastructure providers (the Australian Access Federation¹⁸, AARNet¹⁹, NCI Australia²⁰, Pawsey²¹, Australian BioCommons²²) via their communication teams. The exact number of researchers potentially reached via these communities is unknown.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Survey Respondents

The survey was open from 1 July 2022 to 14 August 2022 and attracted 156 complete responses. Only one respondent did not complete the survey.

3.1.1 Demographics

Of the 157 survey respondents, 142 (90.4%) identified as researchers and 59 (37.8%) identified as research software engineers (RSEs) (Figure 1) (Table 1). An RSE is defined in our survey as “someone who combines software engineering expertise with an intimate understanding of research”. 48 respondents identified as both researchers and RSEs. Most researchers did not identify as RSEs; however, most RSEs did identify as researchers. 4 additional respondents did not identify as either researchers or RSEs. Given that >90% of respondents identified as researchers, the survey showed itself to be well targeted to the community of interest.

Approximately three-quarters of respondents (76.9%, 120) identified that they produce code and/or research software (156 respondents, 1 person omitted the question). See Figure 1. This distribution of responses was very similar to that seen in the original Hucka and Graham study, where 81% of the 69 respondents were involved in software development. In our survey, of the 142 researchers who completed the survey, 106 (75%) indicated that they wrote code/ research software, compared to all 59 of the RSEs.

Other earlier studies have identified that ~30–50% of researchers generate research code/software during their research^{7/23}, which is less than the 77% identified in our study. The apparent increase in researchers generating research software/code could be attributed to the inevitable digital transformation of research, which sees generational changes in the rates at which individuals adopt new digital technologies²⁴. The difference might also be explained by the mailing lists used by the ARDC, which were generated through engagement with the research software program team, and thus already focused on a population of researchers with an interest in research software.

Figure 1. Survey respondents Demographics. Of the 157 survey respondent demographics, 142 (90.4%) identified as researchers. About three-quarters of respondents (76.9%) 120 identified that they produce code and/ or research software and 59 (37.8%) identified as research software engineers (RSEs). 48 respondents identified as researchers, producing code and being RSEs (31%).

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Survey respondents demographics. Total of 157 respondents and three subgroups, researchers, those who write code and those who consider themselves Research Software Engineers.

ARE YOU A RESEARCHER?	DO YOU WRITE CODE?	DO YOU CONSIDER YOURSELF AN RSE?	COUNTS
No	No	No	1
No	Yes	No	3
No	Yes	Yes	11
Yes	–	–	1
Yes	No	No	35
Yes	Yes	No	58
Yes	Yes	Yes	48
Yes: 142 No: 15	Yes: 120 No: 36 NA: 1	Yes: 59 No: 97 NA: 1	157
Yes: 90.4% No: 9.6%	Yes: 76.9% No: 23.1% NA: 1 (Total 156)	Yes: 37.8% No: 62.2% NA: 1 (Total 156)	100%

3.1.2 Domain Expertise

The top 3 domains identified in the 2018 Hucka and Graham study were physical sciences (57%), computing and mathematical sciences (46%) and biology & biological engineering (27%). It is somewhat challenging to compare these domain distributions with ours because computing and mathematical sciences are separate Fields of Research (FoR) codes in the Australian system. Also, Hucka and Graham make no distinction between biology and engineering. The top 3 domains associated with our survey respondents were health sciences (24%), information and computing sciences (20%) and biological sciences (19%) (Figure 2).

A new cohort of respondents was identified in our study in the group representing health sciences (24%) and biomedical and clinical sciences (13%). The next group of respondents represented Earth sciences (16%) and environmental sciences (11%), which could be seen as rough complements to the geological and planetary sciences respondents (3%) of the Hucka and Graham study. Importantly, we had respondents from domains such as human society (10%) and psychology (7%), and could therefore give us some insight into how humanities, arts and social sciences (HASS) and Indigenous research domains affect the survey results when compared to the Hucka and Graham study, which was heavy on science, technology, engineering and mathematical sciences (STEM) and did not include respondents from the social sciences. However, it is clear that respondents to our survey selected FoR codes more frequently associated with STEM disciplines (77%).

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2. Fields of Research (FoR) codes associated with survey respondents. The top 3 domains associated with our survey respondents fields of research codes were Health Sciences (24%), Information and Computing Sciences (20%) and Biological Sciences (19%).

The information and computing sciences domain was represented by 20% (30) of our respondents and, of these, 90% (27 respondents) indicated that they wrote code. About half of all respondents associated with a single FoR code, but the others associated with multiple disciplines. This multidisciplinary was often associated with closely related disciplines, such as biomedical and clinical sciences with health sciences, and environmental sciences with earth sciences. Multidisciplinary, which was also identified in Hucka and Graham’s respondents (35%), was most commonly displayed in our survey by RSEs (Figure 3). Our survey results support a view that RSEs, might work across several research fields, as they seldom work on a single research project over the long term. Reports suggest that research groups typically need — or can afford — research software engineering services on an ad hoc basis²⁵.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3. Number of fields of research associated with researchers and RSE. Many respondents, especially research software engineers (RSEs) are associated with more than one field of research.

To be able to work further with our respondents’ domain spread, we grouped respondents according to the ARDC’s strategic thematic research data commons (‘thematic RDCs’). The ARDC is currently establishing thematic RDCs in Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences (HASS) and Indigenous studies (the HASS RDC and Indigenous Research Capability or IRC²⁶), health research (the People RDC²⁷) and environmental research (the Planet RDC²⁸). To generate these cohort views, we isolated and clustered responses according to the affiliation of their field of research (FoR), to the Planet RDC (24 respondents), the People RDC (28 respondents) and the HASS RDC (26 respondents)²⁹. With these domain clusters, we were able to identify that more environmental researchers (79%) and health researchers (75%) wrote code than researchers in HASS and Indigenous studies (38%) (Figure 4)³⁰. As such, it is important to remember that our observations made in line with a domain may be influenced by the number of coders vs non-coders within that domain.

Figure 4. The ratio of coding researchers to non-coding researchers by domain, clustered in the 3 thematic RDCs.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1.3 Software Engineering and Coding Expertise

To determine the experience of the 120 respondents who identified that they wrote code and/or research software, we asked for how many years they had been doing this, whether for work or for personal projects. While this was an optional question, 119 participants responded. The results indicated that many had been writing code and research software for between 10 and 20 years (Figure 5), with the average experience being between 5–10 years and 10–20 years.

Figure 5. Respondents' years of experience writing code/developing research software (those who identified as coders). Dotted line indicates average response rate.

This data suggests most respondents were probably mid-career, as was the distribution in the Hucka and Graham study. Determining the career stage from this data is challenging, however, because a person who has been coding for 10 years may have started coding early in school and may, therefore, still be an early-career researcher. Our results do indicate that inexperienced coders are less represented in our data, however, which limits the extent to which we can assign behaviours to expertise levels. The “born digital” generation may well have very different approaches to finding and reusing code and research software to older generations, which we cannot explore here. Further studies targeting more junior researchers would be valuable, as they will be the end users of any long-term national or global infrastructure influenced by today’s research software agendas.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Finally, we analysed our respondents programming preferences. Python was the most popular language in use by our survey respondents (64%), followed by R (43%) and Shell scripting (31%) (Appendix A). The 3 pieces of research software that survey respondents indicated they needed access to for the long term were aligned to these programming preferences (Appendix B).

3.2 How Important is Code and Software to Research?

A useful question to better understand researchers' engagement with code and research software was to ask how important this was to their research. This question was presented to researchers only and 79% stated that code and/or research software was essential to their research (Figure 6). This is in line with other reports indicating >90% of researchers use research software³¹, and 65% of US postdoctoral researchers previously surveyed were unable to do their research without it³².

Figure 6. The importance of code and/or research software to respondents. 79% of researchers surveyed stated that code and/or research software was essential to their research.

From our survey results, and those of prior surveys, it is clear that research software is fundamental to research and therefore needs to be valued, maintained, and made discoverable and accessible for the long term.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.3 Code and Research Software Usage Behaviours

3.3.1 Why do Researchers Look for Code/Research Software?

This was a multiple-choice question, with options presented in random order. For most respondents, the efficiency gains from reuse were the most important factors when searching for code and research software (Figure 7). These efficiency gains included the effort saved in developing the software or code themselves (78%) and the ability to analyse their data in more productive ways (64%). Learning was also a motivation, with respondents searching for examples of new algorithms and data structures (46%), and ways to implement these (62%). Many respondents (62%) identified that their existing tools were simply insufficient for their analysis requirements. Some reasons for searching suggested in our “other” category included being able to modify and combine existing code and software in building applications; and that their current tools were no longer supported, insecure or did not support the runtime environment.

Figure 7. Reasons respondents search for code/research software. For most respondents, the efficiency gains from reuse were the most important drivers.

Our results are aligned to those reported by Umarji and Sim³³, who surveyed programmers to understand how and why they searched for source code. Their results indicated that motivations for searching for code included code reuse without modification, looking for reference examples, and looking for resolutions to defects. A more recent study examining researchers’ code-sharing and code-reuse practices identified that 48% of respondents looked for code to directly reuse the code and to reuse selected parts of the code³⁴.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.3.2 How do Researchers Go About Finding Code/Research Software?

All 157 respondents answered this question, which had options presented in random order.

The vast majority (83%) of respondents use general-purpose search systems (for example, Google, Yahoo and Bing) to find code and research software (Figure 8), making clear the need for software infrastructure providers to optimise for search engine discovery. This result is in keeping with the Umarji and Sim study and the Hucka and Graham study where most (87% and 91%, respectively) respondents used a general-purpose search engine such as Google or Yahoo to search for source code. Asking colleagues for recommendations (70%) and searching public software project repositories (62%) were also popular responses. Again, this correlates to the results observed in the Hucka and Graham study, which saw “asking colleagues” (53%) as the second-highest response with a tie for third between “consulting the literature” and “searching in repositories such as SourceForge, GitHub and BitBucket” (45% each).

Figure 8. Mechanisms respondents use to find code/research software. The vast majority (83%) of respondents indicated that they use general-purpose search systems (for example, Google, Yahoo and Bing).

One observation specific to the Australian environment is the low direct usage of ARDC’s Research Data Australia (RDA)³⁵ for code and research software discovery. There are a couple of possibilities for this. To date, RDA has highlighted its capabilities on research data, rather than its capabilities relating to software. RDA is also mostly populated by automated machine-to-machine data feeds from data providers, many of which have yet to be updated to include research software elements. A drive to update the automated metadata capture feeds from providers might be considered, and a marketing campaign to highlight RDA’s research software and code capabilities.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In analysing the differences in search behaviours between coders and non-coders (Figure 9), we identified that coders (68%) were more likely than non-coders (36%) to search for code/software on public software project repositories, possibly due to a lack of awareness of these repositories by non-coders. Non-coders (28%) were more likely than coders (4%) to search in institutional or university repositories. There is therefore an opportunity for research institutions to help non-coding researchers by enhancing their institutional repositories to showcase code and research software available for reuse.

Figure 9. The differences between how coders and non-coders search for code/research software. Respondents who identified as coders (68%) were more likely than non-coders (36%) to search for code/software on public software project repositories. Non-coders (28%) were more likely than coders (4%) to search in institutional or university repositories.

The use of domain-specific (topical) research software registries did not rate highly (31%), an observation also made in the Hucka and Graham study (25%). These authors hypothesised that:

- A. people expect Google to index the topical registries and thus include these results, or
- B. people viewed topical registries as too narrowly focused, or
- C. people are unaware of the existence of topical registries.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 10. The use of topical software registries/catalogues by respondents working in a single discipline. Two-thirds indicated that they do not use topical software registries when searching for code/software.

We carried out limited, deeper analysis to assess whether this observation was simply a result of 69% of our respondents not being associated with disciplines where topical software registries exist. We first had to isolate the respondents that had limited their disciplinary association to a single FoR code (80 of 157 respondents), so that the data was representative of a disciplinary view. From this subset of respondents, we identified those who indicated they made use of topical registries, and thus assumed that such a registry existed for their particular FoR. For these FoRs, we then determined the percentage of respondents that had indicated that they made use of a topical registry (Figure 10). We found that two-thirds (66%) of respondents did not make use of topical software registries. Further research is needed to explore the underlying reasons behind these observations, which could include a lack of registry awareness or a lack of expertise in using such a registry.

We also wanted to determine if any domain differences were apparent in the way that researchers searched for code and software. By examining the 3 thematic RDC domains subsets (People, Planet, HASS), we were able to identify that environmental researchers were more likely than HASS or health researchers to make use of public software project repositories and look at dependencies in code/software (Figure 11). HASS and Indigenous studies researchers, on the other hand, were more likely to search for code and software in institutional repositories than health and environmental researchers, further highlighting the opportunity to enhance institutional repositories to reflect code and software holdings.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 11. Approaches used by respondents to search for code/research software – by the 3 thematic RDCs (People, Planet, HASS). Researchers from the Planet RDC were more likely than HASS RDC researchers or People RDC researchers to make use of public software project repositories and look at dependencies in code/software. HASS and Indigenous studies researchers, on the other hand, were more likely to search for code and software in institutional repositories than People and Planet researchers.

Both the Umarji and Sim and the Hucka and Graham studies demonstrated that only very few respondents reported using a code-specific search engine. In our study, we did not specifically ask the question on code-specific search engines (such as Google Code Search³⁶) but a few respondents (5%) indicated they made use of generalist code repositories, such as Code Ocean³⁷ and Software Heritage³⁸. A couple of “other” responses outlining how researchers find code/research software included researcher websites discovered through links in publications, and repositories managed by vendors of proprietary software, such as Wolfram Mathematica³⁹. This proprietary repository option is related to that also identified by Hucka and Graham in their “other” discovery, which identified that network-based software package installation systems, such as the systems available for Linux operating system distributions, were being used to find software.

Taken together, our survey results and those of others suggest that code-specific and research-software-specific resources are not heavily used by the research community. As such, work to mature the FAIRness (the degree of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability) of research software, particularly its findability, could focus on

- ensuring that research code/software is easily findable using generalist search engines
- enhancing institutional repositories with code and research software holdings.

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At present, repositories specific to code and research software have yet to show any major uptake among the communities that would benefit from them. Further research into why these repositories and catalogues might be out of reach of researchers should be carried out to help inform how best to provide such services to these communities in need.

3.3.3 What Factors Hinder the Findability of Code/Research Software?

All respondents answered this question designed to identify challenges to finding code/research software (Figure 12). The 2018 survey by Hucka and Graham gave us 6 possible responses to the question, one of which (“lack of time to do a proper search and/or evaluate the results”) we split into 2 questions, as we viewed these aspects as distinct. We added “lack of knowledge in how to search” and “challenges in collaborative arrangements when requesting code access” as options.

Figure 12. The hindrances to finding code and research software

The top hindrance to finding code/research software — “lack of references or no availability of the code mentioned in the paper” — highlights how important academic publishing is in driving respondents to search for code and research software. It is often code or research software that they have encountered in a publication that they look for and their search is hampered by too few or no references to access the code (42%). This behaviour is in keeping with that observed by Cadwallader and Hrynaszkiewicz, who identified that 70% of their survey respondents looked at code to help them understand the article they are reading⁴⁰.

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The top hindrance in Hucka and Graham’s study was “unable to locate suitable software”, which was not an option we offered as a response, as we did not view this as an adequate answer to the question, “What *factors* have hindered your ability to find code/research software in the past?”; we wanted to be more specific with our offered responses. However, both the original study and ours identified that the second-highest-rated response was that the respondent’s requirements were “unique” (41%). The Hucka and Graham study identified a higher proportion of people selecting this option (63%) which may reflect the disciplinary differences between our respondents. It is also possible that our offering of additional answer options to this question diluted the responses provided.

Time factors, in keeping with Hucka and Graham’s results, were the third highest hindrance to finding code and or research software (28%). We identified that most researchers searched for code/software every few months (Appendix C); however, to better understand this hindrance it would be useful in future analysis to determine the length of time it takes for people to search. This relates in part to our finding that in >25% of cases, respondents did not know how to search for code and research software. If people don’t know how to search, neither will they know how much time it will take, which may deter them from getting started. Lack of collaboration was also an apparent issue in finding code and research software, with 22% of respondents indicating that their requests for access went unanswered.

As with the Hucka and Graham study, the least common response to hindrances in finding code and research software was that relating to policies (10%). This is perhaps in keeping with an earlier question in our survey about “freedom to choose software” which revealed that institutional policies were not inhibitory here (see Appendix D). Responses provided in our “other” category suggested that the question was not fully understood; rather than hindrances to findability, many of these “other” responses were more aligned with hindrances to *usage* of found code or research software, which we aimed to examine in our analysis of other questions (Appendix E). Of these “other” responses, 4 respondents indicated that they had not had any issues in finding code or software, or “at least something along the lines” of what they were looking for.

When we analysed the factors that hinder coding researchers vs non-coding researchers from finding code and research software, some differences were identified (Figure 14). Non-coding researchers highlighted that their most significant challenges were that they did not have the time to search (43%) and did not have the skill to search (49%) or to evaluate search results (37%). Coding researchers identified that specific requirements being too unique was much more of a hindrance than non-coding researchers did.

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Figure 13. The hindrances to finding code and research software – by cohort (coders/non-coders). Non-coding researchers and coding researchers reported different hindrances to finding code/research software.

When we look at the responses across our HASS, Planet (environment) and People (health) thematic RDCs, we can see that environmental researchers report being challenged by a lack of references or code availability in publications more than health researchers and especially more than HASS researchers (Figure 14). Environmental researchers also indicated that they struggled with a lack of responses to their access requests more than health or HASS researchers. It is unclear whether these observations reflect that there are fewer references to code in HASS and health publications than in environmental research publications; further research would be required to explore this. Health and environmental researchers identified that the uniqueness of their specific requirements was a factor, whereas this did not impact HASS researchers to the same extent. HASS researchers described a more significant lack of skill or knowledge in knowing how to search, and in evaluating the search results, than environmental researchers reported. Health researchers were also challenged in knowing how to search for code and software. Collaborating with the HASS and Indigenous studies research communities and health research communities on introductory approaches to searching for code and software would be valuable. Trust in the software discovered was also raised as a concern, more for HASS and health researchers, which perhaps reflects the potentially sensitive nature of their research.

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Figure 14. *Hindrances to finding code/research software – by domain (People, Planet, HASS/Indigenous). Environmental researchers report the lack of references or code availability in publications as more of a hindrance than other researchers, especially HASS researchers who were more hindered by their lack of skills in searching.*

3.3.4 What Characteristics are Used when Searching or Selecting Code/Research Software?

This question was optional, options were randomly presented, and respondents were requested to skip the question if they hadn't previously considered it. The question was answered by 156 of 157 respondents (Figure 15).

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Figure 15. Importance of characteristics of the code/software respondents look for. Almost all respondents chose 'fit for purpose' as the most important characteristic, followed by price.

Fit for purpose via specific functionality was a very important characteristic that respondents looked for in research software and code (74%, 24% somewhat important). Without this information it is impossible for researchers to know if the software could be useful for their required purpose. Hucka and Graham also identified this attribute as being the most important, with the availability of specific features (96%) being the highest-ranked criterion. Price is also a very important characteristic (70%), a finding supported by Hucka and Graham's study (91%). Research funding is competitive and finite, and concerns of project budget limitations are understandable. Documentation was rated third (65%, very important). This is in keeping with the results of Lawrence et al. who identified documentation availability as the highest-ranked factor (49%) for researchers adopting a new technology⁴¹. Documentation helps researchers use software/code and is a valuable troubleshooting resource in the absence of support from the authors or maintainers.

"Similarity to software previously used" was not deemed particularly important by our respondents (~45% unimportant), reflecting that researchers are often working at knowledge frontiers and are accustomed to working with the unknown. Interestingly, what respondents didn't select is also informative. Respondents were asked to skip any characteristics that they hadn't previously considered and the characteristic most commonly skipped was 'security'. While only 7 of 156 skipped this characteristic and 52% rated it somewhat important, there are potential implications for domains that work with sensitive data. These respondents identified with a number of FoR codes, including biological sciences, information and computing sciences, health sciences and psychology.

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Figure 16. Importance of code/software characteristics sought – by cohort. Non-coding researchers valued the characteristics of software that align to robustness and quality the most, while coding researchers valued open source code and programming language

When examining which characteristics were identified as important, we compared those who said they code vs those who didn't. Coding researchers valued open-source code and software (70%), the availability of source code (51%) and the programming language used in the implementation (55%) far more than non-coding researchers (Figure 16). Non-coding researchers, on the other hand, valued routine maintenance (77%), speed (60%) and security (49%) of code/research software more than coding researchers. Overall, non-coding researchers valued the characteristics of software that align to robustness and quality the most, while coding researchers valued software features, price, and related technical capabilities.

3.3.5 What Information Would Be Most Useful in a Catalogue of Code and Research Software?

Answer options for this question were presented in random order, with 156 respondents answering this question.

Understandably, most respondents (76%) indicated that the purpose of the software would be the most important attribute to list in a catalogue or registry of research software (Figure 17). This aligns to the view that this was a very important characteristic when searching for code (Figure 15), and also aligns to the results seen by Hucka and Graham. Interestingly, price was the second most important characteristic listed when searching for code, and while we did not offer price as an option to this question, one might have anticipated this would be raised in the "other" option, but it was not. We did observe that documentation, as the third most important characteristic when searching for code or research software, was raised as "other" here, when it was not provided as an option.

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Figure 17. *The information that respondents would most like to see in a catalogue of code/research software. The purpose and supported operating system(s) of the code/software were the most popular.*

The size of the user community was the least important piece of information that a registry or catalogue of research software and code might provide (26%). One could hypothesise that, as researchers are often lone pioneers in their chosen topic of research, they are accustomed to working in a more independent manner.

The supported operating system(s) was our second most valued piece of information to sit in a catalogue of research software and code (71%), despite this only being the ninth most important characteristic when searching for code and research software. A similar distinction was seen for data formats supported (66%), with this not rating overly highly when searching for code. Perhaps these differences might be explained by the expectation that a service deliberately designed to catalogue research software and code should list as many characteristics as possible to help interested parties appreciate the breadth and capability of the code/software.

Information that coders and non-coders would like to see in a catalogue/registry differed in some characteristics (Figure 18). 77% of coders had an interest in what software language the software was written in, compared to 31% of non-coders. Similarly, 67% of coders had an interest in the source code availability as opposed to only 22% of non-coders. Non-coders, on the other hand, valued the availability of support (69%) much more than coders (37%), and whether the installation uses common facilities or dependencies (53% non-coders, 33% coders).

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Figure 18. Information that respondents would like to see in a software catalogue/registry – by cohort (coders/non-coders)

When searching for code, the most important aspect seems to be the ability to identify the most critical piece of functionality one needs, and a registry should provide an instant view of many other attributes deemed important.

3.3.6 How is Code and/or Research Software Reuse Enabled?

We wanted to further explore how respondents were making code and research software available for reuse by others. This question was put to the 120 respondents who code, and was answered by 119.

The results reflect the challenges we uncovered for code and software findability (Figure 19). Our data suggest that best practice on citation for code and research software in the form of a Citation File Format (CFF) is yet to gain broad uptake in the research community, as the format is relatively new⁴². Of those 15 respondents making use of CFFs, 9 identified as RSEs.

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Figure 19. How respondents go about sharing their code/research software. Almost two-thirds (61%) indicated that they shared their code and research software publicly.

Almost two-thirds (61%) of respondents indicated that they shared code and research software publicly. It would be useful to further question this cohort in a follow-up survey as it is unclear whether they selected this as encompassing multiple options, e.g. sharing with collaborators, citing in publications, and sharing with those who request it. Further detail on what ‘publicly’ entails would be useful here. More than half (55%) of respondents selected that they shared their code and research software outputs with collaborators. It would also be interesting to dig deeper here to understand how they share with collaborators; are they sharing at the research group level only? Is research software or code shared with collaborators via email? How this approach differs from that of sharing code and research software with those who request it (40%) would also be useful to further explore to perhaps break down barriers there. More information about sharing practices is presented in Appendix F.

40% of respondents indicated that they made the research outputs available via software repositories and registries. Working with repositories and registries to better showcase their holdings would be valuable here. The need for more robust sharing arrangements such as those enabled by licensing were identified by 29% of respondents. Greater awareness of the benefits of licensing to ensure appropriate attribution for any software or code reuse would be valuable too.

We also asked what factors hindered the reusability of code, with lack of documentation (68%) and an inability to install and run the software (52%) being the greatest hindrances (Appendix E).

The survey results suggest that code and research software *findability* is a greater challenge than *reusability* as few respondents indicated that they did not make their outputs available for reuse. If code and research software are being made available for reuse, a lack of reuse could be attributed to it not being findable or understood. Finally, further efforts could be made with those (~10%) who do not share, or do not know how to share, their code and research software outputs.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Our survey respondents overwhelmingly identified research software and code as being essential to their research.

The main reasons they look for code and research software were to save effort and time. When searching for code or research software, most respondents used general-purpose search engines such as Google, asked peers for recommendations, explored public software project repositories, and/or relied on traditional research methods such as literature searches. It is clear that there is an opportunity for software infrastructure providers to optimise for general-purpose search engines to enhance the discovery of their holdings, as researchers make use of these discovery mechanisms the most. The use of topical software registries or catalogues did not rate highly with our respondents, and further research to explore this observation could help domain infrastructure providers offer more tailored resources to their target research end users. We also identified differences in domain impacts which could be further leveraged by infrastructure providers. For example, differences in searching behaviours and the hindrances encountered were identified across environmental, health and HASS and Indigenous research cohorts. Exploring these domain-specific research software challenges would benefit those collaborating across domains.

The top challenges in searching for code and research software were lack of references in the published literature, the uniqueness of the searcher's requirements and a lack of time to search. The main barriers to reuse of code or research software were related to the lack of documentation, inability to install or run software, and a lack of required functionality. In helping researchers with their research software and code challenges, it is worth considering their coding capabilities, because hindrances experienced by coders and non-coders differ. There is an opportunity for research institutions to enhance their institutional repositories to showcase available code and research software to better assist their non-coding researchers, as over a quarter of non-coding respondents made use of these. There are also opportunities to assist non-coders to build skills relating to software searching and confidently evaluating the results of such searches, as these were raised as hindrances by non-coders.

Coders and non-coders also differ in the characteristics that they value when searching for code and software, with non-coding researchers valuing robustness and quality and coding researchers valuing more the software features, price, and related technical capabilities. Overall, the most important characteristics identified by our respondents when looking for code and research software were features, price and availability of documentation. In line with the characteristics that researchers used to search for code and software, 10 specific features were identified by over 50% of respondents as being useful for inclusion in a registry or catalogue of code and research software, with the top 3 being software purpose, supported operating system(s) and supported data formats. There is opportunity for research software infrastructure providers to enhance their capabilities according to these attributes identified as desirable.

The survey results reveal several challenges to research software findability and reusability, some relating to discoverable characteristics of research software, and some to researcher behaviours. Both would benefit from being addressed so that the research sector can gain the efficiencies afforded by the reuse of existing research software and code.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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FEEDBACK

We welcome your feedback on this guide. Please email contact@ardc.edu.au with any comments or questions.

ABOUT THE AUSTRALIAN RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) enables the Australian research community and industry access to nationally significant, data intensive digital research infrastructure, platforms, skills and collections of high quality data.

The ARDC is supported by the Australian Government through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

APPENDIX A. Preferred Programming Languages

119 respondents who code answered our multiple-choice question on which programming and/or scripting language(s) they used most (Figure 20). Python was the most popular language in use (64%), followed by R (43%) and shell scripting (31%). This is in line with the observation by Hucka and Graham, whose respondents also favoured Python the most (59%).

Our survey respondents used different programming and/or scripting language(s) based on the length of their experience. Coders with more years' experience used languages such as C/C++ more than recent coders, who were more comfortable using Python and R. Python is favoured for its data science capabilities, while R is favoured for its statistical capabilities⁴³.

Figure 20. Programming/scripting languages used by respondents. Python was the most popular language in use (64%), followed by R (43%) and shell scripting (31%).

Python was popular across all expertise ranges and has broad uptake across academic communities⁴⁴. It has been described as a good introductory language as it is easy to learn, has good libraries and can be quickly re-run without the need for re-compilation⁴⁵. Java, C/C++ and C# require code to be compiled first, leaving users with a longer time to see any results of code or code changes.

Our respondents identified other programming and/or scripting languages that we had not considered to include as pre-populated answers. 4% of respondents indicated they use Stata, and 3% use Rust. Stata has strengths as statistical software for data science,³⁰ and Rust emphasises code performance and safety⁴⁶.

APPENDIX B. Long-term Access to Research Software

We asked survey participants what 3 pieces of research software they anticipate requiring long-term access to (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Wordcloud represents the research software that respondents anticipate requiring long-term access to.

R (1st) and Python (2nd) dominate the research software options that researchers want long-term access to. This is in keeping with the programming languages that they indicated they used most (Appendix A). Several Python-related libraries were also named as being required longer term (for example, NumPy (3rd), Pandas, PyTorch, SciPy, AstroPy and PsychoPy). Followed by Stata (4th), NVivo (5th), and SPSS (6th), 3 proprietary solutions. With proprietary research software, research reproducibility is inhibited unless a researcher has the funds available to purchase the software.

Commercial entities such as Google (Scholar⁴⁷ and Cloud⁴⁸) were also raised as being required for long-term research productivity, each by one respondent. This demonstrates that they are making progress in the academic community. Finally, it was clear that it is not only data analysis software that is required longer term, with software more traditionally represented in academia, such as Zotero and EndNote, being listed as needed.

Research Software specific to bioinformatics were identified more strongly than for other disciplines, likely to be an artefact of our direct communication of the survey with the Australian BioCommons community.

APPENDIX C. Frequency of Searching for Research Software

We asked survey participants how often they search online for software source code. All 157 survey respondents answered this question. Respondents demonstrated variable behaviours when it comes to searching for software source code online (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Frequency with which respondents search for source code.
Most respondents searched online for source code every few months.

31% respondents searched for source code every few months, possibly because of the cycle time it takes to implement the new code, run it, and determine if it is fit for the research purpose. Hucka and Graham included this question to save those selecting “never” from seeing further questions specific to searching for source code. While this specific conditional filtering was not used in our survey, the question provided a useful insight into the behaviours of our respondents. Our interest here was in identifying any differences in behaviours in our 2 cohorts: researchers and RSEs.

Results suggest that RSEs search online for code more frequently than researchers (Figure 23). Researchers, on the whole, carry out numerous activities such as writing publications and grant proposals, and generating and analysing data; thus they are likely to have less time to spend on coding and research software. RSEs, on the other hand, mostly spend their working days engineering research software and code; thus they are likely to spend a lot more time looking for source code online.

APPENDIX C. Frequency of Searching for Research Software

Figure 23. Frequency with which respondents search for code/research software – by cohort (RSEs/researchers). RSEs search online for code more frequently than researchers.

While the results to this question are interesting, it would be useful for a follow-up study to determine how long it actually takes respondents to search for research software and code. The impacts of searching daily for 5 minutes versus 3 hours are significant. Understanding this effort and time drain on research communities would help to determine what efficiency gains might be made, and thus help the business case for better findability of research software and code. Finally, a small number of respondents indicated that they never search for code and research software online.

APPENDIX D. Freedom to Choose Research Software

We asked survey participants how much freedom they have to choose the code/software that they use. This was important for us to establish because if the respondents had been completely restricted in the research software and code that they were able to use, this would have limited the usefulness of their answers to our following questions about research software and code reuse.

Most respondents (64%) had complete freedom to choose the software or code that they might use in their research (Figure 24).

Given that many IT departments, for understandable security reasons, exert some control over what can and cannot be installed on institutional equipment, it is interesting to see the academic community is not restricted here (<1%). This may reflect a lack of restrictive policy, or perhaps, more favourably, an appreciation that academic innovation might be stifled with restriction, despite the potential security implications. Hucka and Graham also reported similar levels of freedom by their survey respondents.

Figure 24. Amount of freedom respondents have in choosing the code/research software they use. Most respondents (64%) reported having complete freedom.

Some researchers indicated they were limited to a domain specific standard in use by a specific domain (7%). Given the drive for more cross-discipline collaboration in research, particularly in Australia, this limitation may affect the possible collaboration with other disciplines. Similarly, being limited to what is in current use by one's research group (11%) inhibits the introduction of new methods, which could stifle innovation. 25% of respondents indicated they were limited to what was available publicly, perhaps relating to observations discussed on the importance of price and open-source status of research software and code.

APPENDIX E. Factors Hindering Reuse of Research Software

We asked our survey respondents what factors might be responsible for them not being able to use code or research software that they had found. Answer options were presented in random order. Six respondents chose to skip this optional question.

Poor documentation was the biggest identified inhibitory factor that prevented researchers and RSEs from reusing research software or code that they might have found online (68%). Some “other” responses provided further detail on the documentation issue by indicating that published code was poorly commented, making it difficult to reuse. An inability to install or run the software (52%) was our next highest reported issue, which was also highlighted in some “other” responses that indicated that some respondents lacked the skills required to install and run the software, particularly those respondents that did not code (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Factors inhibiting respondents’ reuse of the code/research software that they found online. Poor documentation was the biggest inhibitor.

Our respondents indicated that a lack of support was inhibitory to their reuse of code or research software (39%). Some factors identified in the “other” responses were that the software was hard to learn, or was only available free of charge for a limited time.

APPENDIX F. Approaches to Sharing Code and Research Software

Figure 26. *Sharing practices of respondents who code. About one-third made their code/research software available and also maintain it for reuse by others.*

We asked survey participants whether they make their code/research software available for others to reuse and, if so, whether they maintain it for others. This question was put to the 120 respondents who indicated that they coded, and was answered by 119.

This question was met with an even distribution of responses (Figure 26):

- About one-third of respondents write code and research software for their own research use.
- One-third write code and research software and make it available for others to reuse.
- One-third write code and research software, make it available, and maintain it for others to reuse.

Respondents who identified solely as researchers were more likely to write code or research software for their own use compared to RSEs (Figure 27). RSEs, in contrast, were more likely than researchers to write code or research software, make it available and maintain it for others to reuse. Of the 41 respondents who indicated that they maintained code for others to reuse, 29 were RSEs.

APPENDIX F. Approaches to Sharing Code and Research Software

Figure 27. Sharing practices of respondents who code – by cohort (RSEs/researchers). RSEs were more likely than researchers to write code or research software, make it available and maintain it for others to reuse.

The drivers affecting behaviours are different for each cohort. Research rewards focus on more traditional metrics such as publications, which drives researchers to focus on these outputs over and above all others. This leaves little time for maintaining code or research software for others to use. RSEs, on the other hand, are less affected by the “publish or perish” system and gain reputational benefits and career progression opportunities from having other researchers use their code and software.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

SURVEY QUESTIONS

To maximise the use and reuse of the survey and its design, the survey questions as presented to respondents are shared on Zenodo.

Stevens & Martinez (2022)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353418>

DE-IDENTIFIED RAW DATA

To enable further analysis and to contextualise the findings in the report, the de-identified raw data set is shared on Zenodo.

ARDC (2022)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353422>

SOURCE CODE

The source code used for reproducing the figures are shared on GitHub and in its archived version on Zenodo.

Martinez (2022)

GitHub: <https://github.com/orchid00/FindingSoftwareSurvey>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353426>

REFERENCES

1. BACKGROUND

- 1 <https://www.researchsoft.org>
- 2 <https://ardc.edu.au/>
- 3 Australian Research Data Commons. (2022). A National Agenda for Research Software (1.0). Zenodo. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378082>
- 4 Howison J, Deelman E, McLennan MJ, Ferreira da Silva R, Herbsleb JD. Understanding the scientific software ecosystem and its impact: current and future measures. *Res. Eval.* 2015; 24(4) 454–470. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvv014>
- 5 Hettrick S, Antonioletti M, Carr L, Chue Hong N, Crouch S, De Roure D, Emsley I, Goble C, Hay A, Inupakutika D, Jackson M, Nenadic A, Parkinson T, Parsons M, Pawlik A, Peru G, Proeme A, Robinson J, Sufi S. UK Research Software Survey 2014. Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh on behalf of Software Sustainability Institute; 2015. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.7488/ds/253>
- 6 Bello M, Galindo-Rueda F. Charting the digital transformation of science: Findings from the 2018 OECD International Survey of Scientific Authors (ISSA2), OECD Science, Technology and Industry Working Papers, No. 2020/03, Paris: OECD Publishing; 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1787/1b06c47c-en>
- 7 Howison J, Herbsleb JD. Scientific software production: incentives and collaboration. Proceedings of the ACM 2011 conference on Computer supported cooperative work (CSCW '11). New York, NY (US): Association for Computing Machinery; 2011(513–522). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1958824.1958904>
- 8 Gunn A, Mintrom M. Measuring research impact in Australia. *Australian Universities' Review.* 2018; 60(1);9–15. Available from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1169172.pdf>
- 9 Stewart CA, Almes GT, Wheeler BC, editors. Cyberinfrastructure software sustainability and reusability: Report from an NSF-funded workshop. Bloomington, IN (US): Indiana University; 2010. Available from: <https://scholarworks.iu.edu/dspace/handle/2022/6701>

- 10 Umarji M, Sim SE. Archetypal internet-scale source code searching. In: Sim SE, Gallardo-Valencia RE, editors. Finding source code on the web for remix and reuse. New York, NY (US): Springer; 2013. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-6596-6_3

- 11 Hucka M, Graham MJ. Software search is not a science, even among scientists: A survey of how scientists and engineers find software. *Journal of Systems & Software.* 2018; (141)171–191. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2018.03.047>

2. SURVEY DESIGN AND DISTRIBUTION

- 12 <https://mailchi.mp/ardc.edu.au/ardc-connect-15-july-2022>
- 13 https://twitter.com/ARDC_AU
- 14 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/australian-research-data-commons>
- 15 <https://sites.google.com/ardc.edu.au/visible-research-software>
- 16 <https://github.com/au-research/Visible-Research-Software/discussions>
- 17 <https://rse-aunz.org>
- 18 <https://aaf.edu.au>
- 19 <https://www.aarnet.edu.au>
- 20 <https://nci.org.au>
- 21 <https://pawsey.org.au>
- 22 <https://www.biocommons.org.au>

3. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- 23 Hettrick S. J., et al. (2014). UK Research Software Survey 2014 [Data set]. 2014. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14809>
- 24 Vogels E. Millennials stand out for their technology use, but older generations also embrace digital life. Washington DC (US): Pew Research Center; 2019. Available from: <https://pewrsr.ch/2A3kD6X>
- 25 Woolston C. Why science needs more research software engineers. *Nature*, 31 May 2022. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-01516-2>
- 26 HASS RDC and IRC <https://ardc.edu.au/program/hass-rdc-indigenous-research-capability/>
- 27 People RDC: <https://ardc.edu.au/program/people-research-data-commons/>

REFERENCES

- 28 Planet RDC: <https://ardc.edu.au/program/planet-research-data-commons/>
- 29 Planet RDC FoR Codes: 37 Earth Sciences, 41 Environmental Sciences, 30 Agricultural, Veterinary and Food Sciences. People RDC FoR codes: 42 Health Sciences, 32 Biomedical and Clinical Sciences. HASS RDC FoR codes: 44 Human Society, 52 Psychology, 47 Language, Communication and Culture, 38 Economics, 39 Education, 43 History, Heritage and Archaeology, 45 Indigenous Studies, 35 Commerce, Management, Tourism and Services, 33 Built Environment and Design, 36 Creative Arts and Writing, 48 Law and Legal Studies, 50 Philosophy and Religious Studies.
- 30 One respondent in the Planet cluster and one in the HASS cluster did not indicate whether they coded
- 31 Hettrick S. softwaresaved/software_in_research_survey_2014: Software in research survey (1.0). 2018. Zenodo. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1183562>
- 32 Nangia U, Katz DS. Track 1 Paper: Surveying the US National Postdoctoral Association regarding software use and training in research. Journal contribution. 2017 Aug 30. figshare. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.5328442.v3>
- 33 Umarji M, Sim SE. Archetypal internet-scale source code searching. In: Sim SE, Gallardo-Valencia RE, editors, Finding source code on the web for remix and reuse. New York, NY (US): Springer. 2013. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-6596-6_3
- 34 Cadwallader L., Hrynaszkiewicz I. A survey of researchers' code sharing and code reuse practices, and assessment of interactive notebook prototypes. OSF Preprints; 2022, March 2. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/tys8>
- 35 <https://researchdata.edu.au>
- 36 <https://code.google.com>
- 37 <https://codeocean.com>
- 38 <https://www.softwareheritage.org>
- 39 <https://resources.wolframcloud.com/FunctionRepository>
- 40 Lawrence KA, Zentner M, Wilkins-Diehr N, Wernert JA, Pierce M, Marru S, Michael S. Science gateways today and tomorrow: positive perspectives of nearly 5000 members of the research community. Concurrency Computat.: Pract. Exper., 2015; (27)4252–4268. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.3526>
- 41 Lawrence KA, Zentner M, Wilkins-Diehr N, Wernert JA, Pierce M, Marru S, Michael S. Science gateways today and tomorrow: positive perspectives of nearly 5000 members of the research community. Concurrency Computat.: Pract. Exper., 2015; (27)4252–4268. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.3526>
- 42 Druskat S, Spaaks JH, Chue Hong N, Haines R, Baker J, Bliven S, Willighagen E, Pérez-Suárez D, Konovalov A. Citation File Format (1.2.0). Zenodo. 2021. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5171937>
- 43 <https://r4stats.com/articles/popularity>
- 44 <https://stackoverflow.blog/2017/09/14/python-growing-quickly/>

APPENDIX B.

Preferred Programming Languages

- 45 <https://www.quora.com/Why-has-Python-become-so-popular-in-academia-superseding-other-languages-like-C-C++-Java-and-C>
- 46 <https://codilime.com/blog/why-is-rust-programming-language-so-popular/>

APPENDIX C.

Long-term Access to Research Software

- 47 <https://scholar.google.com>
- 48 <https://cloud.google.com>

Australian Research Data Commons

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